

A FORECAST OF THE NUMBER OF EASTERN ORTHODOX IN AUSTRALIA IN 2051

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Abstract

The purpose of this report is to provide a forecast of the numbers of Eastern Orthodox through to 2036. The projection is based on the official Census data from 1911 to 2021. It is estimated that by 2051 - in theory- the number of Eastern Orthodox in Australia will be 728,339 with a 95% confidence lower-bound of 570,673 and a 95% confidence upper-bound of 886,006.

Keywords

Eastern Orthodox, Australia, census

I. INTRODUCTION

It is a brave person that attempts to forecast any social phenomenon such as religious affiliation well into the future. If the results are confirmed as accurate then some will respond, "Of course, naturally!" or "It was expected" or "I told you so". If the forecaster is in error - as is likely to be the case - then people will cast scorn and derision on the forecaster.

Long-term religious affiliation is difficult to predict because it can be influenced by the rate of "switching" to no religion as well as demographic factors such as the age structure, birth rates or migration. The purpose of this paper is to attempt a forecast using simple linear regression through to 2051 of the numbers of Eastern Orthodox. The projections are based on the official census data from 1911 through to 2021.

TABLE 1

Eastern Orthodox – Australia 2021

Group	Number
Albanian Orthodox	16
Antiochian Orthodox	14264
Greek Orthodox	390963
Macedonian Orthodox	52311
Romanian Orthodox	2147
Russian Orthodox	22631
Serbian Orthodox	48287
Ukrainian Orthodox	2627
Eastern Orthodox - other	2213

By way of background, the category of Eastern Orthodox is a heterogeneous group that comprises: Albanian Orthodox, Antiochian Orthodox, Greek Orthodox, Macedonian Orthodox, Romanian Orthodox, Russian Orthodox, Serbian Orthodox,

Ukrainian Orthodox. At the last 2021 Census, Eastern Orthodox numbered 535,470 and made up 2.1% of the population. By far the largest group within this cohort is Greek Orthodox at around 390,963. The breakdown across the groups is shown in Table 1.

The number of Eastern Orthodox as a proportion of the population reached its peak at 2.89% in 1981 and has been declining consistently thereafter, although individual groups within this cohort (e.g., Greek Orthodox, Serbian Orthodox) have different trajectories. The proportion of Eastern Orthodox in the Australian population is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Eastern Orthodox as a proportion of the Australian population 1911-2021

II. METHOD

A forecast through to 2051 of future Eastern Orthodox affiliation was based on the historical data from 1911-2021 in Table 1 of the Appendix. A line of best fit indicating the 95 percent confidence level was determined.

TABLE 2

Eastern Orthodox in Australia: 2026-2051

Year	Estimate	95% lower-bound	95% upper-bound
2026	568342	498369	638316
2031	600342	506155	694528
2036	632341	518963	745720
2041	664341	534544	794137
2046	696340	551950	840730
2051	728340	570673	886006

II. RESULTS

By 2051, it is forecast that the number of Eastern Orthodox in Australia will be 728,839. The projections are summarised in Table 2 and illustrated with 95% confidence intervals in Figure 2. Further results and statistical values are provided in the Appendix.

Figure 2. Eastern Orthodox projection to 2051 (with confidence intervals)

III. CONCLUSIONS

The conclusion of this research report is fairly simple: the numbers of Eastern Orthodox are expected to grow, with the forecast being an additional 192,870. At most it might increase by 350,536 to 886,006 or at least by 35,203 to 570,673. The future composition of the Eastern Orthodox is not known but it is likely that there will remain a large Greek, Macedonian and Serbian influence since they already account for 491,594 out of the existing 535,470 Eastern Orthodox. The proportion of Orthodox in the general population will continue to remain small.

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REFERENCES

Australian Bureau of Statistics. (2022, July 4). *Religious affiliation in Australia*. ABS. <https://www.abs.gov.au/articles/religious-affiliation-Australia>.

APPENDIX TABLE 1

Eastern Orthodox 1921-2021

Year	Eastern Orthodox
1911	2646
1921	5372
1933	8435
1947	17012
1954	74745
1961	154924
1966	255500
1971	338632
1976	372200
1981	421300
1986	427400
1991	474800
1996	497000
2001	529400
2006	544163
2011	563072
2016	502801
2021	535470

Appendix Figure 1. Eastern Orthodox 1911-2021

Appendix Figure 2. Eastern Orthodox projections to 2051.

APPENDIX TABLE 2

Statistical values

Statistic	Value
Alpha	0.90
Beta	0.00
Gamma	0.00
MASE	0.78
SMAPE	0.04
MAE	22,117.21
RMSE	34,250.36

Explanations:

1. Alpha (base value) - the smoothing value between 0 and 1 that controls the weighting of data points. The higher the value, the more weight is given to recent data.
2. Beta (trend value) - the value between 0 and 1 that determines the trend calculation. The higher the value, the more weight is given to recent trends.
3. Gamma (seasonality value) - the value between 0 and 1 that controls the seasonality of the ETS forecast. The higher the value, the more weight is given to the recent seasonal period.
4. MASE (mean absolute scaled error) - a measure of the forecast accuracy. $MASE < 1$ implies that the forecast performs better.
5. SMAPE (symmetric mean absolute percentage error) - a measure of accuracy based on percentage or relative errors. SMAPE has a lower bound of 0% and an upper bound of 200%.
6. MAE (mean absolute error) - measures the average magnitude of the prediction errors, regardless of their direction. A common measure of the forecast error.
7. RMSE (root mean square error) - a measure of the differences between the predicted and observed values (Sources for explanations: ablebits.com and numxl.com Retrieved October 2022)